

Supplementary materials for:

Integrated water resources management in Indonesia: Lessons learned and future challenges

Ainul Firdatun Nisaa^{a*} and B. V. Tangahu^a

^aDepartment of Environmental Engineering, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember, Surabaya, Indonesia

Department of Environmental Engineering, Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember, Surabaya 60111, Indonesia; firdatun@its.ac.id *corresponding author

A. Data sources for the proportion of the population with appropriate drinking water access and sanitation access

An appropriate drinking water access refers to an approved drinking water source, including piped water, protected water sources (boreholes, wells, springs), and rainwater. Data on population number, drinking water, and sanitation access per province are based on the National Socioeconomic Survey (Susenas) and sourced from the Statistical Yearbook of Indonesia (BPS-Statistics Indonesia 2021a). Data is available for all 34 provinces, but Papua is omitted from the graph as the percentage is relatively low (drinking water 62.73% and sanitation access 40.31%).

Table 1. Number of populations, improved drinking water, and sanitation access per province in 2020*

Province	Island	Population	Sanitation (%)	Drinking water (%)
Aceh	Sumatra	5,274,871	77.06	87.66
North Sumatra	Sumatra	14,799,361	81.08	89.68
West Sumatra	Sumatra	5,534,472	68.11	83.37
Riau	Sumatra	6,394,087	83.99	88.25
Jambi	Sumatra	3,548,228	77.82	78.86
South Sumatra	Sumatra	8,467,432	76.94	80.78
Bengkulu	Sumatra	2,010,670	78.10	62.47
Lampung	Sumatra	9,007,848	78.81	74.97
Bangka Belitung Islands	Sumatra	1,455,678	92.58	75.06
Riau Islands	Sumatra	2,064,564	89.19	90.41
Jakarta (DKI)	Java	10,562,088	93.04	99.84
West Java	Java	48,274,162	71.40	93.42
Central Java	Java	36,516,035	83.24	94.07
Yogyakarta (DI)	Java	3,668,719	96.96	96.02
East Java	Java	40,665,696	80.98	95.56
Banten	Java	11,904,562	82.00	92.87
Bali	Bali - Nusa Tenggara	4,317,404	95.01	97.36
West Nusa Tenggara	Bali - Nusa Tenggara	5,320,092	82.89	94.13
East Nusa Tenggara	Bali - Nusa Tenggara	5,325,566	69.70	83.87
West Kalimantan	Kalimantan	5,414,390	75.81	78.83
Central Kalimantan	Kalimantan	2,669,969	72.31	74.91
South Kalimantan	Kalimantan	4,073,584	81.17	70.36
East Kalimantan	Kalimantan	3,766,039	89.17	85.51
North Kalimantan	Kalimantan	701,814	82.09	89.50
North Sulawesi	Sulawesi	2,621,923	85.49	90.31
Central Sulawesi	Sulawesi	2,985,734	74.61	84.60
South Sulawesi	Sulawesi	9,073,509	88.96	90.84
Southeast Sulawesi	Sulawesi	2,624,875	82.38	92.49
Gorontalo	Sulawesi	1,171,681	75.68	94.16
West Sulawesi	Sulawesi	1,419,229	77.07	72.75
Maluku	Maluku	1,848,923	75.06	91.68
North Maluku	Maluku	1,282,937	75.99	86.90
West Papua	Papua	1,134,068	78.71	79.56
Papua	Papua	4,303,707	40.31	62.73

*based on the BPS-Statistics Indonesia (2021a)

B. Data sources and calculations of groundwater usage

Drinking water in Indonesia originates from groundwater and non-groundwater sources (surface water and rainwater). The drinking water source from groundwater comes in various forms: pumped water, bottled water, protected and unprotected wells, protected and unprotected springs, and some of the piped water supplied by the local water utility. For this calculation, we assume that 50% of the piped water is originated from groundwater. Data for groundwater usage is based on the National Socioeconomic Survey (Susenas) and sourced from the Statistical Yearbook of Indonesia (BPS-Statistics Indonesia 2021a; 2001).

Table 2. Number of populations and groundwater-sourced drinking water per province in 2000 and 2020**

Province	Island	Population	Groundwater-sourced in 2000	Groundwater-sourced in 2020
North Sumatra	Sumatra	14,799,361	80.95	89.79
Jakarta (DKI)	Java	10,562,088	76.94	95.62
West Java	Java	48,274,162	92.11	96.62
Central Java	Java	36,516,035	90.41	90.96
East Java	Java	40,665,696	88.11	95.24
East Nusa Tenggara	Bali - Nusa Tenggara	5,325,566	82.72	87.00
West Kalimantan	Kalimantan	5,414,390	20.05	49.42
South Sulawesi	Sulawesi	9,073,509	84.84	89.94
Maluku	Maluku	1,848,923	-	91.11
Papua	Papua	4,303,707	62.45	75.17

**based on the BPS-Statistics Indonesia (2021a; 2001)

References

BPS-Statistics Indonesia, 2021a. *Statistics Indonesia 2021 (English: Statistical Yearbook of Indonesia 2021)*. Jakarta, Indonesia: Badan Pusat Statistik.

BPS-Statistics Indonesia, 2001. *Statistics Indonesia 2000 (English: Statistical Yearbook of Indonesia 2000)*. Jakarta, Indonesia: Badan Pusat Statistik.